

Perception of Communication Competence in First MBBS Students: The Crucial Role of AETCOM TrainingSamata Padaki¹, Amrut Dambal², Sukanya Badami³, S Prabin⁴, Sumangala Patil⁵, Anita Herur⁶¹Associate Professor & HOD, Department of Physiology, Gadag Institute of Medical Sciences, Gadag²Professor & HOD, Department of Biochemistry, JGMMMC, Hubballi³Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Gadag Institute of Medical Sciences, Gadag⁴Postgraduate student, Department of Physiology, Gadag Institute of Medical Sciences, Gadag⁵Professor, Department of Physiology, BLDE (DU), Vijayapura⁶Professor, Department of Physiology, S. Nijalingappa Medical College, Bagalkot

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Abstract:

Basic Science forms the keystone in the building block of the Medical Profession. Students understand the context of basic science when taught in relevance to the clinical aspects. Competency-Based Medical Education (CBME) has introduced Attitude, Ethics and Communication in the MBBS curriculum to change the professional conduct of Medical students. This study aimed to evaluate the perception of communication skills among first MBBS students after effective AETCOM learning sessions. The "Communication Skills Attitude Scale" (CSAS) assessed a cross-sectional study involving undergraduate medical students' attitudes toward learning communication skills. The CSAS questionnaire was added to a Google form, and the link was sent to the students. The response was analyzed by using a percentage scale. The perception of 66 students was presented in terms of percentage on a five-point Likert Scale. Students perceived communication skills as important for gaining knowledge and essential in doctor-patient interaction. Communication skill training forms a basis for the Doctor-Patient interaction and can be learned at the undergraduate level.

Keywords: Competency-Based Medical Education (CBME), AETCOM, Communication Skills Attitude Scale.

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Introduction

The Indian Medical Graduate (IMG) is expected to be a clinician, leader of a health team, communicator, lifelong learner and professional. The ability to communicate effectively is a core competency for medical practitioners. The effective communication skills of healthcare professionals are pivotal in ensuring positive patient outcomes, enhancing patient satisfaction, and fostering collaboration within healthcare teams. Inculcating habits of good communication skills during formative years is not just beneficial, but essential for medical students in the future.

One of the five roles of an Indian Medical Graduate (IMG) is to be a good Communicator. In India, the National Medical Commission (NMC) has recognized the importance of communication as a core competency in medical education. This led to introducing the Attitude, Ethics, and Communication (AETCOM) module as part of the undergraduate MBBS curriculum. [1] AETCOM aims to equip students with essential skills in patient interaction, empathy, and ethical decision-

making, which are crucial for professional success. As medical educators, curriculum developers, and healthcare professionals, our role in shaping and refining the AETCOM module is crucial to its success. Basic Science forms the keystone in the building block of the Medical Profession. Students understand the context of basic science when taught in relevance with the clinical aspects during their formative years. Traditional medical teaching imparts theoretical and practical knowledge of disease processes. It educates them about diagnostic and treatment modalities but does not address communication skills essential in dealing with patients.

This study focuses on assessing the perception of communication skills among first-year MBBS students after undergoing AETCOM training. Understanding students' self-assessment of their communication abilities after completing this module can provide insights into the effectiveness of the curriculum and inform future enhancements. It is essential to explore how students perceive their

competencies in communicating with patients, peers, and faculty and how this perception evolves post-training. The research will contribute to evidence-based recommendations for optimizing medical curricula to better address the communication challenges faced by budding doctors in real-world clinical settings. Hence, this study evaluated the perception of communication skills among first-year MBBS students after effective AETCOM learning sessions.

Material and Method

A cross-sectional study was conducted at Gadag Institute of Medical Sciences, Gadag, among first-year undergraduate medical students from September to October 2022. Institutional ethical clearance was obtained by the Institutional Ethics Committee priorly. The study was taken up after the sessions on AETCOM Module 1.4: The foundations of communication – 1. This module was chosen as a prerequisite for the study due to its comprehensive coverage of the fundamental principles of communication in medical education.

The perception of students towards communication skills was assessed by the “Communication Skills

Attitude Scale” (CSAS). [2] The CSAS questionnaire was modified and made suitable to first-year students by removing 8 questions out of 26; few were positively worded (e.g., “To be a good doctor I must have good communication skills” – item 1) and few negatively (e.g., “I don’t need good communication skills to be a doctor” – item 11) arranged randomly. The CSAS questionnaire was shared with the students using a Google form link. The students, who were keen to contribute to the study, were asked to share their responses.

The perception of the students was analyzed using a five-point Likert scale. Each statement was rated as “Strongly disagree,” “Disagree,” “Neutral,” “Agree,” and “Strongly agree” and was numbered from 1 to 5, respectively. Responses from 66 students were recorded, and the data was analyzed using SPSS software through a percentage evaluation.

Results

66 students shared their response to the study. The perception of students in terms of percentage to the questionnaire provided is presented in the Table 1.

Table 1: Perception of students in terms of percentage to the CSAS questionnaire.

Sl. No	Questions	1 = Strongly Disagree (%)	2 = Disagree (%)	3 = Neutral (%)	4 = Agree (%)	5 = Strongly Agree (%)
1.	In order to be a good doctor, I must have good communication skills.	0	0	0	23.4	76.6
2.	Developing my communication skills is just as important as developing my knowledge of medicine.	0	0	3.1	51.6	45.3
3.	Learning communication skills has helped or will help me respect patients.	1.6	0	1.6	43.8	53.1
4.	I haven’t got time to learn communication skills	20.3	56.3	15.6	7.8	0
5.	Learning communication skills is interesting.	0	3.1	6.3	64.1	26.6
6.	Learning communication skills has helped or will help facilitate my team-working skills.	0	0	1.6	48.4	50
7.	Learning communication skills is fun.	0	7.9	19	60.3	12.7
8.	Learning communication skills has helped or will help me respect my colleagues.	0	0	4.7	50	45.3
9.	Learning communication skills has helped or will help me recognize patients’ rights regarding confidentiality and informed consent in future.	0	0	3.1	65.6	31.3
10.	When applying for medicine, I thought it was really a good idea to learn communication skills.	0	8.1	12.9	50	29
11.	I don’t need good communication skills to be a doctor.	50.8	42.9	6.3	0	0
12.	I find it hard to admit having some	4.8	27.4	38.7	27.4	1.6

	problems with my communication skills.					
13.	I think it's really useful learning communication skills on the medical degree.	0	0	1.6	49.2	49.2
14.	My ability to pass exams will get me through medical school rather than my ability to communicate.	6.3	42.9	31.7	15.9	3.2
15.	Learning communication skills is applicable to learning medicine.	0	1.6	19	61.9	17.5
16.	I find it difficult to take communication skills learning seriously.	4.8	61.9	25.4	7.9	0
17.	Learning communication skill is important because my ability to communicate is a lifelong skill.	0	0	3.2	39.7	57.1
18.	Communication skills learning should be left to psychology students, not medical students.	34.4	59	6.6	0	0

Discussion

Communication is a critical skill for healthcare providers. Effective communication improves patient outcomes, enhances patient satisfaction, and promotes team collaboration. Therefore, integrating communication training into medical curricula is crucial. The introduction of AETCOM in the MBBS program has been transformative, fostering these skills, especially in the early stages of medical education.

Our study revealed that after AETCOM training, students not only showed increased confidence and improved understanding of patient-centered care, but also a profound transformation in their approach to medical practice. Early exposure to communication modules aids in developing empathy and ethical responsibility in medical practice. In our study, students perceived the need for good communication skills to be good physicians. It was also perceived that communication skills were as necessary as gaining knowledge and most essential in doctor-patient interaction. This is supported by studies by Maguire et al., [3] Zolnierek et al. [4] and Hausberg et al. [5]

Learning communication skills is not just a part of the curriculum, but a lifelong process that is essential for healthcare professionals. It not only helps in teamwork and improves their ability to communicate with patients, but also ensures continuous professional development. This is similar to a study by Vinod Kumar et al. [6]. Most students felt that learning to communicate would be a lifelong process that was much needed along with the curriculum.

The increased level of mistrust of the general public on the medical professionals due to negligence, misconduct, and unethical practices leading to violence and legal complications is a

pressing issue. It underscores the dire need for igniting ethics and communication skills. [6,7,8] By enhancing these skills, we cannot only improve patient care but also rebuild public trust in the healthcare system. The selection procedure for a medical course in our country does not consider the humanitarian attitude of a candidate, which is much needed to become a doctor. Hence, CBME, a system that focuses on the outcomes of education and the abilities of the students, has been introduced in the undergraduate curriculum. It includes Attitude, Ethics and Communication training to change the professional conduct of Medical students.

Conclusion

The study emphasizes the transformative role of AETCOM (Attitude, Ethics, and Communication) training in shaping the perceptions of first-year MBBS students about communication skills. This well-structured module, introduced early in their medical education, has the potential to significantly enhance their awareness and comprehension of meaningful communication in medical practice. This transformative training equips future practitioners to build compassionate, ethical, and effective relationships with patients, thereby revolutionizing the way healthcare is delivered.

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